

A Reproducible Framework to Publish and Reuse Collections as Data

The Case of the European Literary Bibliography

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GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) institutions host rich content that is provided in the form of digital collections. Bibliographic databases are collections of references focused on a particular topic that can be used to apply digital humanities (DH) methods. Recent approaches, such as Collections as Data and Labs, promote the publication of digital collections supporting computational use.

This paper aims to provide a framework for publishing and reusing digital collections based on literary bibliographies published by GLAM institutions and make them suitable for computational use in the form of Collections as Data, drawing in particular on the European Literary Bibliography (ELB). It also describes the infrastructure used and possible DH research scenarios to illustrate how the results can be reused for different goals. Digital curators and DH researchers interested in making their datasets available in the form of Collections as Data are the intended audience of this work.

Keywords: GLAM Labs, bibliographic data, Collections as Data, reproducible code, Jupyter Notebooks

Reprodukowalny model publikowania i ponownego wykorzystywania kolekcji jako danych: przypadek Europejskiej Bibliografii Literackiej

Abstrakt

Instytucje GLAM (Galerie, Biblioteki, Archiwa i Muzea) udostępniają bogate zasoby w postaci kolekcji cyfrowych. Bazy danych bibliograficznych to zbiory odniesień skoncentrowanych wokół określonych tematów, które mogą być wykorzystywane w przez Humanistykę Cyfrową (Digital Humanities, DH). Nowoczesne podejścia, takie jak Collections as Data oraz GLAM Labs, promują publikację kolekcji cyfrowych umożliwiającą zastosowania obliczeniowe. Celem niniejszej pracy jest przedstawienie workflow poświęconego publikacji i ponownemu wykorzystaniu kolekcji cyfrowych w formie Collections as Data, stworzonych na bazie bibliografii literackiej. Dane, pochodzące z Europejskiej Bibliografii Literackiej, zostały dostosowane do potrzeb badań obliczeniowych. Praca opisuje także wykorzystaną infrastrukturę oraz przedstawia scenariusze badań DH, ilustrując, jak uzyskane wyniki mogą być wykorzystane do różnych celów. Adresatami niniejszej pracy są cyfrowi kuratorzy oraz badacze DH zainteresowani udostępnianiem swoich zbiorów w formie Collections as Data.

Słowa kluczowe: GLAM Labs, dane bibliograficzne, kolekcje jako dane (Collections as Data), odtwarzalny kod, Jupyter Notebooks

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Conflict of Interest

The authors do not have any conflict of interest to declare

INTRODUCTION

GLAMs (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) have been exploring new ways to make their content available. They have used a wide diversity of techniques and methods in order to facilitate the reuse of their rich content, which includes text, images, postcards, metadata, literary bibliographies, videos, audio and maps. Advances in technology have provided a new environment in which high-quality and interoperable data is required for different purposes, such as the application of Natural Language Processing and machine learning (Tasovac, Chambers, and Tóth-Czifra 2020; Candela 2023a). In this context, new initiatives, such as Labs and Collections as Data (Mahey et al. 2019; Padilla et al. 2019), have emerged to promote the publication and reuse of digital collections in innovative and creative ways. Computational access refers to the application of techniques such as network analysis, Named Entity Recognition and Entity Linking.¹

In the context of GLAMs and digital humanities (DH), bibliographic databases are a significant type of content, consisting of curated collections of references centred around a specific topic. Several initiatives focus on the open-access publication of aggregated bibliographic databases that use literary studies as their main content. A wide diversity exists in both the provision of metadata and the tools and services available for browsing the data (Umerle et al. 2022). In order to foster cooperation between all the parties involved (e.g. data curators and researchers), community-led efforts have been established. These include the Bibliographical Data Working Group (BiblioData WG), set up in the context of the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH).

This paper aims to provide a framework for publishing and reusing digital collections based on literary bibliographies published by GLAM institutions to make them suitable for computational use in the form of Collections as Data.² Digital curators and DH researchers interested in making their datasets available in the form of Collections as Data are the intended audience of this work.

Our main contributions are (a) a framework to publish and reuse Collections as Data based on bibliographic metadata; (b) the results obtained using the proposed infrastructure, including reproducible code; and (c) a selection of DH research scenarios illustrating how the data could be explored and reused. These contributions are intended to leverage the adoption of Collections as Data by GLAM institutions providing detailed documentation and code, as well as additional use cases based on bibliographic metadata.

Our argument is structured as follows: after a brief overview of the publication of Collections as Data in the GLAM sector, we introduce the framework employed for publishing and reusing Collections as Data based on bibliographic metadata, as well as the results obtained after its application. The article concludes with a brief summary of the proposed framework and outlines potential avenues for future research.

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1. See, for example, the International GLAM Labs computational access section available at <https://glamlabs.io/computational-access-to-digital-collections/>.
 2. A glossary is provided at the end of this paper to facilitate the definition of technical words relevant for this research.

RELATED WORK

GLAM institutions have been adopting the Collections as Data principles to make their digital collections available and suitable for computational access and use (Chambers et al. 2023). Collections as Data combine FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance³ to foster interoperability and responsible use of data (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Carroll et al. 2020). Previous works have focused on the requirements for standardising documentation that describes cultural heritage datasets in the form of datasheets, in order to facilitate their reuse by the community (Alkemade et al. 2023). For example, the Berlin State Library recently published a digital collection that includes bibliographic metadata and documentation in the form of datasheets to stimulate research and development in artificial intelligence applications (Schneider and Lehmann 2024).

A checklist was recently published as a collaborative approach to facilitate the publication of Collections as Data by small and medium-sized institutions (Candela et al. 2023). Lee (2025) has also published a detailed checklist that includes guidelines and best practices for machine learning projects using data from cultural heritage. In addition, the Research Data Alliance recently created an interest group focused on the use and publication of Collections as Data.⁴

Previous works have tackled the publication of interoperable digital collections suitable for computational use in the GLAM domain. In general, the datasets are available in traditional formats such as Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC).⁵ Several examples build on the Semantic Web, an initiative promoted by Tim Berners-Lee in the '00s (Berners-Lee, Hendler, and Lassila 2001). The Semantic Web uses standardised vocabularies such as the Resource Description Framework (RDF) (World Wide Web Consortium 2014), which describes and enriches metadata obtained as a result of Linked Open Data (LOD). Several vocabularies, ontologies and conceptual models have recently been made available to publish metadata. These include the Bibliographic Framework Initiative (BIBFRAME), the Library Reference Model (LRM), the Bibliographic Ontology (BIBO) and Schema.org (Coyle 2022; World Wide Web Schema.org Community Group 2024). OCLC promotes the use of Linked Data in order to make library services more interconnected, accessible and useful (OCLC 2024).

For example, the National Library of Scotland has explored the use of the Semantic Web in datasets provided by the Data Foundry (Candela 2023b). In addition, and given the relevance of providing high-quality data in the current context, several approaches are based on the data quality assessment of LOD repositories made available by DH institutions using data quality criteria SPARQL and Shape Expressions (ShEx) (Candela 2023a). Other examples have transformed biographical collections, such as the Finnish National Biography, into LOD to explore various data analyses (Tamper et al. 2023). Museums and archives like the Rijksmuseum and the Zeri Photo Archive have also explored the use of the Semantic Web to make their content available as LOD (Dijkshoorn et al. 2018; Daquino et al. 2017). Additional projects have focused on the publication of epistolary data, the data quality

3. CARE is an acronym that stands for collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics.

4. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rationale/collections-as-data-ig>

5. <https://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic>

assessment of records and the exploration of visualisation approaches (Hyvönen, Leskinen, and Tuominen 2023; Vega-Gorgojo 2024; Pasquale et al. 2024). In a similar way, the national libraries of France, Spain and the Netherlands have made their digital catalogues available in the form of LOD using different ontologies and vocabularies (e.g. LRM and Schema.org). In addition to the Virtual International Authority File (VIAF), Wikidata has emerged as a leading repository with which to enrich the catalogues (Candela et al. 2024).

Concerning bibliographic content, examples include the Bibliography of Scottish Literature in Translation (BOSLIT⁶)—made available by the National Library of Scotland—the Polish Literary Bibliography⁷ and the Czech Literary Bibliography.⁸ Other catalogues, such as the Library of Congress⁹ and the Universiteitsbibliotheek Gent,¹⁰ are published in the form of dump files. A notable example of utilising data from the GLAM sector is the European Literary Bibliography (ELB) (Umerle and Malínek 2022),¹¹ which compiles multilingual bibliographic data covering both literature and literary studies from Czechia, Poland, Finland and Spain. This initiative not only reflects the unique characteristics of GLAM institutions, but also aligns with the interests of scholarly communication.

In this context, GLAM institutions have begun to promote responsible and transparent use of their digital collections (National Library of the Netherlands 2024; National Library of Scotland 2024). *Jupyter Notebooks* have emerged as a powerful tool for GLAMs to provide (i) rich documentation about their digital collections, (ii) reproducible code showing how to access the data, and (iii) charts and interactive widgets (Sherratt 2021; Candela, Chambers, and Sherratt 2023).¹² Previous work has addressed the quality assessment of Jupyter Notebook projects providing best practices and guidelines (Pimentel et al. 2021). In addition, GLAM institutions, such as the Library of Congress, have started to make documentation and reproducible code available to increase the visibility and use of their digital collections (Library of Congress 2024).

These efforts provide a more comprehensive demonstration of how digital collections have been made available by GLAM institutions, including different types of material, such as metadata and bibliographic content. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, none of this research employs a reproducible framework to publish bibliographic metadata as LOD according to the Collections as Data principles and including research scenarios as use cases. Such an approach aims to leverage the Semantic Web and encourage GLAM institutions to adopt these technologies in order to facilitate the publication of digital collections in the form of Collections as Data.

6. <https://data.nls.uk/data/metadata-collections/boslit/>

7. <https://pbl.ibl.waw.pl/>

8. <https://clb.ucl.cas.cz/en/>

9. www.loc.gov/item/2020445551

10. lib.ugent.be/info/exports

11. <https://literarybibliography.eu/>

12. Reproducibility refers to the ability to replicate the results of an experiment (Pimentel et al. 2021).

A REPRODUCIBLE FRAMEWORK TO TRANSFORM BIBLIOGRAPHIC METADATA INTO COLLECTIONS AS DATA

The framework proposed in this paper to transform bibliographic metadata into Collections as Data works in six steps. Figure 1 provides an overview of the main steps included in the framework. Each step is described in the following sections.

Figure 1: Framework employed to transform bibliographic metadata into Collections as Data.

DATA EXTRACTION

The first step involves selecting the required data according to a particular theme, such as an author, organisation or motif, which is a repeated pattern that reappears throughout the narrative. GLAM institutions have started to make their digital collections available under open licence in different ways to promote their reuse. For example, they have created new sections called Labs in which they provide data, examples of use and prototypes. Some examples include the Data Foundry at the National Library of Scotland,¹³ the Library of Congress Labs¹⁴ and the National Library of Luxembourg.¹⁵

In some cases the data is available as dump files, making it easier to access. More advanced approaches are based on the use of Application Programming Interfaces (API), as adopted at the Museum of Modern Art in New York,¹⁶ the National Library of France¹⁷ and the Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes.¹⁸ Other initiatives, such as Europeana, provide a File Transfer Protocol (FTP) server to download metadata collections as ZIP files.¹⁹

In general, researchers might be interested in a portion of a dataset rather than the entire content. The ELB, for example, provides an interface that enables users to select and extract data using filters. The data extracted consists of a ZIP file comprising the content (e.g. metadata, text or images).

Research repositories are another type of GLAM initiative to make datasets available.²⁰ Other data publication platforms are Zenodo,²¹ the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Open Marketplace²² and Wikidata.

13. <https://data.nls.uk>

14. <https://labs.loc.gov>

15. <https://data.bnl.lu>

16. <https://api.moma.org>

17. <https://data.bnf.fr>

18. <https://data.cervantesvirtual.com>

19. <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/harvesting-and-downloads>

20. See, for example, the British Library research repository available at <https://bl.iro.bl.uk>.

21. See, for example, the Metadata of the “Alter Realkatalog” bibliographic dataset made available by the Berlin State Library (Schneider and Lehmann 2024).

22. <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu>

As a result of the extraction process, different formats (e.g. JSON or CSV) and files (e.g. a unique file or different files per entity, such as Person and Work) can be obtained. When using standard metadata formats, existing packages like `pymarc`²³ can be used to extract the required metadata, such as titles, subjects and authors (Candela 2023b). CSV is a common format for providing data in the form of a list of columns according to the metadata fields. Additional formats can be obtained as a result of the extraction process, for example JSON, XML and text.

DATA MODELLING

Data modelling refers to the way extracted data is modelled using ontologies and vocabularies to provide machine-readable and enriched bibliographic metadata. An analysis of the classes and properties provided by the vocabularies and ontologies introduced in section was performed to identify the best option. As a result, Schema.org—a standardised vocabulary to describe data and content on web pages—was selected for its understandability, ease of adoption and widespread use within the community. It provides a simple representation of the works compared to more complex initiatives such as BIBFRAME and LRM, in which works are described using several layers (e.g. work, expression and manifestation) (Coyle 2022).

Figure 2 describes the main classes and properties used for the data modelling process. A resource with the type `schema:Dataset` is related to a resource with the type `schema:CreativeWork`, employing a `schema:isPartOf` property. Each resource with the type `schema:CreativeWork` can be refined into a more specialised class provided by the vocabulary, including `schema:Chapter`, `schema:Journal` and `schema:Book`. Resources with the type `schema:CreativeWork` are related to resources with the type `schema:Person` and `schema:Place` through the particular properties `schema:author` and `schema:spatial`, respectively. In addition, in some cases, resources with the type `schema:Person` and `schema:Place` are enriched with external repositories such as Wikidata and VIAF by means of the property `owl:sameAs`.

Figure 2: Overview of classes and properties used to describe bibliographic metadata based on the vocabulary Schema.org.

TRANSFORMATION AND ENRICHMENT

Transformation to LOD requires the employment of RDF to describe the metadata in the form of triples. Several packages are available to create and use RDF data,

23. <https://pymarc.readthedocs.io>

```

# create empty graph
g = Graph()

# add namespaces
schema = Namespace("https://schema.org/")
g.bind("schema", schema)

# define default domain
domain = 'https://example.org/'

# define type of resource
classtype = 'https://schema.org/CreativeWork'

# create resources
record = URIRef(domain + "record/" + str(row['id']))
g.add((record, RDF.type, URIRef(classtype)))
g.add((record, schema.isPartOf, libri))
g.add((record, schema.identifier, Literal(row['id'])))
g.add((record, schema.name, Literal(row['title'])))

```

Listing 1: Overview of Python code based on the package RDFLib and the ontology Schema.org to create the RDF based on the data sources.

for example [RDFLib](#)²⁴ and SPARQL Endpoint Interface to Python.²⁵ Other packages, such as Apache Jena,²⁶ are based on the use of Java as a programming language. In addition, RDF data can be serialised to different formats such as [RDF/XML](#), [Turtle](#) or [JSON-LD](#). Listing 1 shows an overview of the Python code based on the package RDFLib to create RDF data.

Concerning enrichment, Wikidata is one of the most highly used repositories to link resources provided by GLAM institutions (Candela et al. 2024). To do so, several properties dedicated to GLAM institutions (e.g. the property <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P268> set up for the National Library of France) have been created in Wikidata, enabling the connection of different types of elements, such as authors and works. In addition, VIAF has been extensively used by institutions to establish links based mainly on authors. In order to establish new links, several methods can be implemented, such as Named Entity Recognition and Entity Linking. Other approaches have focused on relation extraction methods to create a knowledge graph from text corpora (Cabot et al. 2023).

According to the data modelling proposed here, listing 2 shows an overview of how the original metadata provided in JSON can be transformed into LOD using Turtle as a serialisation format. It shows the metadata of a resource with the type `schema:Book` and a resource with the type `schema:Person`. Both resources are identified by Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI). Additional properties, such as `schema:author`, are used to define relationships between authors and their works. Depending on the richness of the source metadata, the author may be represented as a literal (e.g. the author's name) or as a URI representing the author. Finally, the property `owl:sameAs` is used to link to external repositories such as Wikidata and VIAF.

24. <https://rdflib.readthedocs.io>

25. <https://sparqlwrapper.readthedocs.io>

26. <https://jena.apache.org/>

```

<https://example.org/record/F3342118> a schema:Book ;
  dc:subject "Grabados",
    "Libros ilustrados",
    "Novelas cortas" ;
  schema:author <https://example.org/person/5682>,
    "Cervantes Saavedra, Miguel de",
    "Hochkofler, Mary de" ;
  schema:datePublished "1928" ;
  schema:identifier "F3342118" ;
  schema:inLanguage <https://example.org/language/es>,
    <https://example.org/language/it> ;
  schema:isPartOf <https://example.org/dataset/libri> ;
  schema:license <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/> ;
  schema:name "Don Chisciotte della Mancia" ;
  schema:spatial <https://example.org/place/Q2044> .

<https://example.org/person/5682> a schema:Person ;
  owl:sameAs wd:Q5682,
    viaf:17220427 ;
  schema:birthDate "1547" ;
  schema:deathDate "1616" ;
  schema:name "Cervantes Saavedra, Miguel de" .

```

Listing 2: Overview of how the original metadata provided in JSON can be transformed into LOD using the data modelling proposed in this work.

DATA QUALITY

Data quality has become crucial to foster the reuse of digital collections (Candela 2023a). One key aspect is to guarantee the high quality of the generated RDF data. ShEx schemas can be generated and tested against the RDF data produced in the previous step to measure its quality. To accomplish these tasks, packages such as *sheXer* (Fernández-Álvarez, Labra-Gayo, and Gayo-Avello 2022) and *PyShEx*²⁷ can be used to define the ShEx schemas and assess the data quality. *SheXer* enables the configuration of several parameters to retrieve, for example, the number of instances, in order to create the ShEx schemas. Users can also indicate the minimum percentage of instances that should conform with a constraint.

Listing 3 shows an overview of the ShEx schemas created automatically using the tool *sheXer*. It shows the percentage of instances that conformed to each constraint as well as the cardinalities (e.g. the character + corresponds to one or more values). The ShEx schema provides two classes—*Book* and *Person*—each of them with a list of constraints defining how they must be described by means of properties (e.g. `schema:author`) and data value types (e.g. `xsd:string`). This ShEx schema can be used to assess that the RDF data generated in the previous step, in particular the resources typed as *Book* and *Person*, are compliant with the defined constraints.

Moreover, the data quality assessment results can be provided as additional documentation using standard vocabularies such as the Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT) (Albertoni and Isaac 2021). Other means can be used to assess RDF data (Király 2024).²⁸

27. <https://pypi.org/project/PyShEx/>

28. See, for example, the data quality analysis available at <https://qa-data.kbr.be/>.

```

ex:Book
{
  rdf:type [schema:Book] ; # 100.0 %
  schema:isPartOf IRI ; # 100.0 %
  schema:sourceOrganization xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  schema:inLanguage xsd:string +; # 100.0 %
  schema:inLanguage @ex:Language +; # 100.0 %
  schema:author xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  schema:author @ex:Person ; # 100.0 %
  schema:license IRI ; # 100.0 %
  schema:genre xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  schema:name xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  schema:datePublished xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  schema:identifier xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  dc:subject xsd:string *
      # 99.96056782334385 % obj: xsd:string. Cardinality: +
}

ex:Person
{
  schema:name xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  owl:sameAs IRI {2}; # 100.0 %
  schema:deathDate xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  schema:birthDate xsd:string ; # 100.0 %
  rdf:type [schema:Person] # 100.0 %
}

```

Listing 3: Overview of the ShEx schemas for the entity `schema:Book` and `schema:Person`, automatically generated using the tool `sheXer`. As a result, `sheXer` provides the percentage of instances that conformed with each constraint.

PUBLICATION

Once the data has been transformed into RDF and its quality assessed, it can be published. When making data available, it is crucial that documentation is provided on aspects such as provenance, licence, content and potential reuses in order to foster its reuse (Alkemade et al. 2023; Candela et al. 2023).

Recent approaches are based on the description of datasets using machine-readable vocabularies, such as `DCAT`, thereby facilitating interoperability across datasets (World Wide Web Consortium 2024).

Datasets can be published in several repositories and platforms, including Labs sections in GLAM, GitHub and GitLab code repositories, GLAM research and data repositories, and collaborative-led approaches such as Wikidata and the SSH Open Marketplace.²⁹ This will increase the visibility of the dataset and foster its reuse by the research community (Candela et al. 2023).

REUSE

Once the dataset has been published in one of the above-mentioned repositories, it can be reused. Several approaches can be followed, such as the implementation of a prototype illustrating how to access and reuse a digital collection in innovative ways. For example, the US Library of Congress recently published the Newspaper Navigator to explore historical newspapers (Lee and Weld 2020). Other approaches

29. <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

provide collections of Jupyter Notebooks showing users how the data can be accessed, including examples of use (Candela, Chambers, and Sherratt 2023).

In addition, research scenarios defined by DH researchers, historians and linguists can be supplied in the form of documentation and reproducible code in order to provide accurate, multidisciplinary and rich use cases.

RESULTS

The framework proposed in section was applied to the ELB, which is available under a CC0 licence. A selection of datasets were extracted according to recognised authors and institutions: (i) the author Adam Mickiewicz, (ii) the author Miguel de Cervantes, and (iii) a larger selection of data from the National Library of Spain. Table 1 shows the results obtained after applying the framework proposed in this work to the selection of datasets.

Dataset	Classes	Properties	No. triples	No. external links
Adam Mickiewicz	7	19	47,631	863
Miguel de Cervantes	5	19	44,389	749
National Library of Spain	7	19	10,515,016	67,563

Table 1: Results obtained after the application of the framework to a selection of datasets from the ELB.

The framework was implemented in the form of a collection of reproducible Jupyter Notebooks that are available for the public as open-source code (Candela, Rosiński, and Arkadiusz 2025).³⁰ Several Python packages were used to create CSV and RDF files as well as validate the generated data and access external repositories. Some examples include RDFLib, pandas³¹ and qwikidata.³² SheXer was used to automatically generate the ShEx schemas using 100 instances, ensuring that at least 70 percent of the instances include the constraint. Figure 3 shows a section of a Jupyter Notebook to transform the original metadata into LOD, which illustrates how the code and documentation are combined. Following the best practices promoted in previous work (Candela, Chambers, and Sherratt 2023), the code repository was published in Wikidata to increase its visibility.³³

Figure ?? shows the architecture used to apply the framework. It shows the main elements, such as the original data, tools and infrastructure employed. Concerning the data, three datasets were extracted as ZIP files based on different authors, institutions and sizes. The infrastructure was provided by the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC),³⁴ an affiliated unit of the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Polish Academy of Sciences. This also ensures the long-term sustainability of the project and includes (i) a GitLab code repository, (ii) a cloud data storage system for the data extracted, and (iii) a JupyterHub server to run the Jupyter Notebooks developed as part of the project. The collection of Jupyter Notebooks was implemented following the best practices and guidelines proposed

30. <https://gitlab.pcsc.pl/dl-team/atrium/tna01>

31. <https://pandas.pydata.org>

32. <https://qwikidata.readthedocs.io>

33. <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q133236883>

34. <https://www.psnc.pl/>

Figure 3: Section of a Jupyter Notebook to transform the original metadata into LOD, illustrating how the code and documentation are combined.

by the research community (e.g. including a README file) (Sherratt 2021; Candela, Chambers, and Sherratt 2023). Finally, several research scenarios were described to show how to reuse the data.

Figure 4: Architecture defined to apply the framework proposed in this work. It focuses on three main elements: data, infrastructure, and publication.

DEFINING RESEARCH SCENARIOS BASED ON THE ELB

The ELB exemplifies how GLAM data can be integrated with considerations of scholarly communication. The purpose of the service is to create an ecosystem for the international processing, integrating, enriching, presenting and sharing of open literary bibliographical datasets (Vimr and Rosiński 2024). The challenges faced by the ELB when aggregating content include selecting the data, structuring the data stored in different formats, using different thesauri and presenting them as an organised structure in a semantic environment. The latter need is already partly addressed by integrating Wikidata identifiers and linking to its resources.

The ELB discovery service improves data comprehension by publishing and reusing digital collections. However, more demanding and nuanced research needs may require solutions, such as a proposed reproducible framework that allows data exploration through SPARQL queries. Data becomes more comprehensible by learning about defined classes and properties. A particular example being the use of the owl : sameAs property. Not only does it help find a link for data in the form of an identifier; it also supports enriched queries that can use several resources.

The effort to make the data collected on the ELB site more accessible allows Collections as Data principles to be expanded to include new issues and respond to the challenges of scholarly content circulation. The use of the Semantic Web

makes it possible to address the challenges of the growing number of publications. The semantic approach enables more efficient tracking of the latest discoveries and trends. It also counteracts the low reproducibility of research by enabling the replication of the scientific process, facilitating knowledge-mining and increasing the availability of data for machine processing (Jaradeh et al. 2019).

The research scenarios provided in the following sections illustrate how the proposed framework can be applied to address specific challenges faced by GLAM institutions when their data is used for scientific purposes. For example, one of the major issues in bibliographic databases is the inconsistency and fragmentation of metadata. Scenarios focus on linking bibliographical resources with external authority databases to increase the possibility of inferring and viewing data. The framework facilitates interoperability by harmonising metadata across different sources using RDF and Schema.org. This facilitates seamless querying as well as reuse of data across various providers, while also ensuring the reproducibility of results.

SCENARIO 1: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PROVINCIAL SPANISH NOVELS FEATURING VAMPIRES

The researcher is interested in the representation of vampires in Spanish novels, with a particular focus on how these themes interact with the centre-periphery relationship, the visibility of smaller localities in the discourse and the category of exclusion. In order to explore the data, the researcher uses the following keywords: *novela española, vampiros, provincia* (Spanish novel, vampires, province).

The researcher can understand a province in two ways: either as a place of action or as a place of publication. In addition, literary texts can provide information about both. Defining a province using the framework can be done by identifying a list of Spanish provincial places by their location or by their number of inhabitants, obtained from Wikidata (property P1082). The prepared list can then be used as a search condition in the title, metadata or text of the work, if available. Spanish novels and vampires can be searched in subjects, as well as titles and notes. The rich non-bibliographic and contextual data devoted to persons and institutions will allow patterns to be found between authors' birthplaces, places of publication and places of action. The possibility of selecting provincial Spanish novels dedicated to vampires opens up opportunities for comparative analysis of the publishing and reading market, and the processes of literary life.

SCENARIO 2: REPUBLICAN WRITERS WHO MIGRATED DURING THE SPANISH CIVIL WAR

Combining bibliographic data with Wikidata resources allows the use of previously unavailable types of data that do not fit into the traditional bibliographic description metadata set, such as the typology of relationships predicates. A research scenario on Republican writers who migrated during the Spanish Civil War can be created using the following properties: country of citizenship (P27), allegiance (P945), place of detention (P2632), conflict (P607) or military unit (P7779). Consideration of the above criteria allows for additional axes of reflection to be formed and, at the same time, enables the over-representation and under-representation of certain categories to be observed, a potentially valuable signpost for data aggregation practices in the GLAM sector.

SCENARIO 3: GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF PUBLICATIONS DEDICATED TO PARTICULAR SPANISH WRITERS

A research scenario at the intersection of GLAM and scholarly communication can be based on the geographical distribution of publications dedicated to particular Spanish writers. In this case, the researcher focuses on the geographical distribution of scholarly texts. Achieving this scope of interest requires constructing a query that considers literary authors as the subjects of scholarly texts and the place of publication of the respective texts. Both writer and place entries in the ELB are provided with Wikidata identifiers so that the results of the query can be enriched and validated by additional metadata. Based on such a query, it is possible to identify leading research centres in order to reflect on particular authors, identify trends and even undertake a synthesis of the literary system by classifying popular and forgotten authors. A complementary query that may help reduce information silos would be to compare the ELB, as a dedicated literary bibliographic resource, with Wikidata, a broadly applicable open data platform, in order to identify Spanish authors absent from the LOD ecosystem.

DISCUSSION

Despite the growing availability of data under open licence, researchers typically focus on specific themes, which are often not adequately reflected in the metadata of library catalogues. In this sense, contextual information provided by external repositories can help integrate additional information. However, metadata generated by collaborative initiatives like Wikidata are rather incomplete and are not standardised (e.g. inconsistent properties are used to describe literary activities such as literary prizes, where the Nike Prize (Q672037) is described as a “literary award” and the Kornel Makuszyński Prize (Q11789099) is described only as an “award”).

Our contribution builds upon bibliographic data made available by GLAM institutions. However, it can be applied to other domains, such as museums and archives, by adapting each of the steps included in the framework to the content provided by the institutions. For example, some adjustments need to be made in order to choose the right ontology to describe a different set of metadata, as well as to select external repositories with which to enrich the collection.

Concerning data acquisition, data can be provided in several ways, such as ZIP files or by means of an API. For data quality assessment and requirements, several approaches can be employed, as described below. In addition, this work has limitations in terms of data, scope and coverage:

- The data generated was based on and limited in scope to the data retrieved from the original source. The data was retrieved in JSON format using ELB’s online interface.
- The domain used to create the URI patterns (e.g. <http://domain.org/>) is there for testing purposes. An existing domain should be used to provide permanent identifiers.
- Depending on the institution selected to extract the data, the metadata are provided in different fields (e.g. geographic information), so the code was adjusted to retrieve the correct information.
- Large datasets are difficult to handle on personal computers when using Jupyter Notebooks. Cloud infrastructure is required to be able to efficiently

process large datasets such as the data provided by the National Library of Spain. Scalability may be challenging for small and medium-sized institutions as they have limited computational resources and capacity (Candela et al. 2023). In this sense, supercomputing centres like the PSNC provide the required infrastructure in terms of data storage and access when processing large volumes of data (e.g. bibliographical data, images, text or sound).

- The data modelling step included in the framework is based on the Schema.org vocabulary that transforms the metadata provided by the ELB. However, this step can be extended and refined using additional vocabularies, classes and properties.
- Based on the original bibliographic metadata, the enrichment step is mainly based on Wikidata and VIAF. Additional repositories like GeoNames and DBpedia could be used to enrich the metadata. Moreover, methods such as Named Entity Recognition and Entity Linking could be used to identify new entities in the original metadata, such as descriptions, subjects, and titles.
- The data quality assessment is limited in scope to the use of ShEx. This can be extended using the existing Data Quality Vocabulary to describe the results of the assessment. Additional work is required in order to employ comparative metrics provided by previous work in terms of completeness and metadata diversity (Király 2024).

The data provided by GLAM institutions is in some cases limited in terms of expressivity and completeness. It does not always meet researchers' needs. For example, after applying the framework in this paper and considering the data provided by the ELB, a user is not limited to the interface facets or original MARC21 structure, but can browse data in a more complex way by combining subject, genre and text fragment. As outlined in the research scenarios, utilising data in a multilevel manner and integrating external resources is essential to meet scientific needs. In addition, the use of federated SPARQL queries may be required and useful to be able to search across repositories.

CONCLUSION

GLAM institutions are starting to publish their digital collections in a form that is suitable for computational access. Best practices and guidelines were recently published to facilitate this transition. In this context, several institutions have explored the use of the Semantic Web and LOD to provide machine-readable and interoperable metadata about their content.

Based on bibliographic content, this contribution provides a reproducible framework to transform traditional bibliographic content into LOD following the Collections as Data principles. The framework was applied to a selection of datasets extracted from the ELB. It included a selection of research scenarios to show both how the data can be reused and its limitations. The framework can be adapted to different repositories to guide the data transformation and enrichment.

Future work to be explored includes the use of additional ontologies and external repositories to describe and enrich the metadata. In addition, the application and adaptation of the framework to other domains, such as museums and archives, will have to be analysed.

INSTALLATION GUIDE

The open code included as part of this work, describing how to implement the framework, can be installed on a computer using the following steps:

- Download the code from the repository: <https://gitlab.pcsc.pl/dl-team/atrium/tna01>.
- Open the folder with the code.
- Run the command: `pip install -r requirements.txt`
- Open Jupyter.
- Open and run the Jupyter Notebooks provided.

The processing of larger datasets (see, for example, the notebooks dedicated to the National Library of Spain) requires the use of additional infrastructure in terms of data storage and memory, such as that provided by the PSNC.

REFERENCES

- Albertoni, Riccardo, and Antoine Isaac. 2021. "Introducing the Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV)." *Semantic Web* 12 (1): 81–97. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-200382>.
- Alkemade, Henk, Steven Claeysens, Giovanni Colavizza, Nuno Freire, Jörg Lehmann, Clemens Neudecker, Giulia Osti, and Daniel van Strien. 2023. "Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets." *Journal of Open Humanities Data* 9 (1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>.
- Berners-Lee, Tim, James Hendler, and Ora Lasila. 2001. "The Semantic Web." *Scientific American Magazine* 284 (May). <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/the-semantic-web/>.
- Cabot, Pere-Lluís Huguet, Simone Tedeschi, Axel-Cyrille Ngonga Ngomo, and Roberto Navigli. 2023. "RED^{FM}: A Filtered and Multilingual Relation Extraction Dataset." In *Proceedings of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers) (Toronto, Canada, 9–14 July)*, edited by Anna Rogers, Jordan L. Boyd-Graber, and Naoaki Okazaki, 4326–4343. Kerrville, Texas: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/2023.ACL-LONG.237>.
- Candela, Gustavo. 2023a. "An Automatic Data Quality Approach to Assess Semantic Data from Cultural Heritage Institutions." *JASIST* 74 (7): 866–878. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ASI.24761>.
- Candela, Gustavo. 2023b. "Towards a Semantic Approach in GLAM Labs: The Case of the Data Foundry at the National Library of Scotland." *Journal of Information Science* 0 (0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515231174386>.
- Candela, Gustavo, Sally Chambers, and Tim Sherratt. 2023. "An Approach to Assess the Quality of Jupyter Projects Published by GLAM Institutions." *JASIST* 74 (13): 1550–1564. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ASI.24835>.
- Candela, Gustavo, Mirjam Cuper, Olga Holownia, Nele Gabriëls, Milena Dobрева, and Mahendra Mahey. 2024. "A Systematic Review of Wikidata in GLAM Institutions: A Labs Approach." In *Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries—28th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, TPD L 2024 (Ljubljana, Slovenia, 24–27 September), Proceedings, Part II*, edited by Apostolos Antonopoulos, Annika Hinze, Benjamin Piwowarski, Mickaël Coustaty, Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio, Francesco Gelati, and Nicholas Vanderschantz, 15178:34–50. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. New York: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-72440-4_4.
- Candela, Gustavo, Nele Gabriëls, Sally Chambers, Milena Dobрева, Sarah Ames, Meghan Ferriter, Neil Fitzgerald, et al. 2023. "A Checklist to Publish Collections as Data in GLAM Institutions." *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*

- (November). <https://doi.org/10.1108/gkmc-06-2023-0195>.
- Candela, Gustavo, Cezary Rosiński, and Margraf Arkadiusz. 2025. "ATRIUM Transnational Access Scheme—A Reproducible Framework to Publish and Reuse Collections as Data: The Case of the European Literary Bibliography." Zenodo. Version March25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15075805>.
- Carroll, Stephanie Russo, Ibrahim Garba, Oscar L. Figueroa-Rodríguez, Jarita Holbrook, Raymond Lovett, Simeon Materechera, Mark A. Parsons, et al. 2020. "The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance." *Data Science Journal* 19 (1): 43. <https://doi.org/10.5334/DSJ-2020-043>.
- Chambers, Sally, Melanie Walsh, Michelle Caswell, Geoff Harder, Mercedes Okumura, Julia Corrin, Gabriela Baeza Ventura, et al. 2023. "Position Statements—Collections as Data: State of the Field and Future Directions." Zenodo. Version 1, 2 May. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897735>.
- Coyle, Karen. 2022. "Works, Expressions, Manifestations, Items: An Ontology." *The Code4Lib Journal* 53. <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/16491>.
- Daquino, Marilena, Francesca Mambelli, Silvio Peroni, Francesca Tomasi, and Fabio Vitali. 2017. "Enhancing Semantic Expressivity in the Cultural Heritage Domain: Exposing the Zeri Photo Archive as Linked Open Data." *ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage* 10 (4): 21:1–21:21. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3051487>.
- Dijkshoorn, Chris, Lizzy Jongma, Lora Aroyo, Jacco van Ossenbruggen, Guus Schreiber, Wesley ter Weele, and Jan Wielemaker. 2018. "The Rijksmuseum Collection as Linked Data." *Semantic Web* 9 (2): 221–230. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-170257>.
- Fernández-Álvarez, Daniel, José Emilio Labra-Gayo, and Daniel Gayo-Avello. 2022. "Automatic Extraction of Shapes using sheXer." *Knowledge-Based Systems* 238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.KNOSYS.2021.107975>.
- Hyvönen, Eero, Petri Leskinen, and Jouni Tuominen. 2023. "LetterSampo—Historical Letters on the Semantic Web: A Framework and Its Application to Publishing and Using Epistolary Data." *ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage* 16 (1): 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569372>.
- Jaradeh, Mohamad Yaser, Sören Auer, Manuel Prinz, Viktor Kovtun, Gábor Kismihók, and Markus Stocker. 2019. "Open Research Knowledge Graph: Towards Machine Actionability in Scholarly Communication." ArXiv. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:59413794>.
- Király, Péter. 2024. "QA Catalogue—A Quality Assessment Tool for Library Catalogues." *GWDG Nachrichten* 04-05:19–24.
- Lee, Benjamin, and Daniel S. Weld. 2020. "Newspaper Navigator: Open Faceted Search for 1.5 Million Images." In *UIST '20 Adjunct: The 33rd Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology (Virtual Event, USA, 20–23 October)*, edited by Shamsi T. Iqbal, Karon E. MacLean, Fanny Chevalier, and Stefanie Mueller, 120–122. New York: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3379350.3416143>.
- Lee, Benjamin Charles Germain. 2025. "The 'Collections as ML Data' Checklist for Machine Learning and Cultural Heritage." *JASIST* 76 (2): 375–396. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24765>.
- Library of Congress. 2024. "Tutorials for Data Exploration." Library of Congress. <https://libraryofcongress.github.io/data-exploration/intro.html>.
- Mahey, Mahendra, Aisha Al-Abdulla, Sarah Ames, Paula Bray, Gustavo Candela, Caleb Derven, Milena DobrevamcPherson, et al. 2019. *Open a GLAM Lab*. Doha, Qatar: International GLAM Labs Community (Book Sprint). <https://doi.org/10.21428/16ac48ec.f54af6ae>.
- National Library of Scotland. 2024. *AI Statement*. Last revised 24 May 2024. <https://www.nls.uk/media/sv0fsflg/national-library-of-scotland-ai-statement.docx>.
- National Library of the Netherlands. 2024. "Statement on Commercial Generative AI." National Library of the Netherlands website. <https://www.kb.nl/en/ai-statement>.

- OCLC. 2024. *Linked Data: The Future of Library Cataloging*. Dublin, OH: OCLC. <https://doi.org/10.25333/71w4-vq71>.
- Padilla, Thomas, Laurie Allen, Hannah Frost, Sarah Potvin, Elizabeth Russey Roke, and Stewart Varner. 2019. “Final Report—Always Already Computational: Collections as Data.” Zenodo. Version 1, 22 May. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3152935>.
- Pasquale, Alessio Di, Valentina Pasqual, Francesca Tomasi, and Fabio Vitali. 2024. “On Assessing Weaker Logical Status Claims in Wikidata Cultural Heritage Records.” *Semantic Web* 15 (6): 2395–2417. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.3233/SW-243686>.
- Pimentel, João Felipe, Leonardo Murta, Vanessa Braganholo, and Juliana Freire. 2021. “Understanding and Improving the Quality and Reproducibility of Jupyter Notebooks.” *Empirical Software Engineering* 26 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10664-021-09961-9>.
- Schneider, Sophie, and Jörg Lehmann. 2024. “Metadata of the ‘Alte Realkatalog (ARK)’ of Berlin State Library (SBB).” Dataset. Zenodo. Version v2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12783813>.
- Sherratt, Tim. 2021. “GLAM Workbench.” Zenodo. Version v1.0.0, 27 October. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5603060>.
- Tamper, Minna, Petri Leskinen, Eero Hyvönen, Risto Valjus, and Kirsi Keravuori. 2023. “Analyzing Biography Collections Historiographically as Linked Data: Case National Biography of Finland.” *Semantic Web* 14 (2): 385–419. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-222887>.
- Tasovac, Toma, Sally Chambers, and Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra. 2020. *Cultural Heritage Data from a Humanities Research Perspective: A DARIAH Position Paper*. DARIAH’s response to European Commission’s evaluation and possible revision of the Commission Recommendation of 27 October 2011 on Digitisation and Online Accessibility of Cultural Material and Digital Preservation (REC 2011/711/EU). October. <https://hal.science/hal-02961317>.
- Umerle, Tomasz, Giovanni Colavizza, Elżbieta Herden, Rindert Jagersma, Péter Király, Beata Koper, Leo Lahti, et al. 2022. *An Analysis of the Current Bibliographical Data Landscape in the Humanities. A Case for the Joint Bibliodata Agendas of Public Stakeholders*. DARIAH-EU Bibliographical Data Working Group report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559857>.
- Umerle, Tomasz, and Vojtěch Malínek. 2022. “Literarybibliography.eu – modelový příklad pro tvorbu mezinárodní oborové bibliografie.” *Česká literatura (Czech Literature)* 70 (5): 579–595. <https://doi.org/10.51305/cl.2022.05.03>.
- Vega-Gorgojo, Guillermo. 2024. “LOD4Culture: Easy Exploration of Cultural Heritage Linked Open Data.” *Semantic Web* 15 (5): 1563–1592. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-233358>.
- Vimr, Ondrej, and Cezary Rosiński. 2024. “Building a European Literary Bibliography. Challenges and Strategies in Integrating and Presenting Multilingual Data.” Paper presented at DH Benelux 2024 (Leuven, Belgium, 4–7 June 2024). Zenodo. Version v1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11454445>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D, Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- World Wide Web Consortium. 2014. *RDF 1.1 Concepts and Abstract Syntax*. Edited by Richard Cyganiak, David Wood, and Markus Lanthaler. W3C. Recommendation 25 February 2014. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>.
- World Wide Web Consortium. 2024. *Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)*. Edited by Riccardo Albertoni, David Browning, Simon JD Cox, Alejandra Gonzalez Beltran, Andrea Perego, and Peter Winstanley. W3C. Version 3. Recommendation 22 August 2024. <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>.
- World Wide Web Schema.org Community Group. 2024. *Schema.org*. Version 29.2. <https://schema.org/>.